

The 20th February Event: Strategies for Education and Economic Development in Cambodia

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ABSTRACT

The Covid-19 is a global challenge by which no country could be spared from the effect. Despite the stumbling block and limited financial and technical resources, Cambodia's success in the fight against Covid-19, particularly upon the 20th February Event, is an untold story and lesson learned for other countries in this brutal battle. The article reports about the Cambodian government's strategies in the outbreak and the consequences of the outcomes of the policies on education and economic sectors. The policies are inclusive of impacts, temporary alternatives, and preparation for recovery, by which resources management and international cooperation play an essential role. Thus, the clear and compelling arrangement and implementation have called for political stability, normalization, and reopening with low Covid-19 cases and high vaccination rates.

Keywords: Covid-19, Cambodia development, 20th February Event.

I. INTRODUCTION

Following December 2019, the Chinese authorities announced the outbreak of an unknown disease, which was later regarded as the coronavirus outbreak or the Covid-19 pandemic, emerging from Hubei, Wuhan of China. The reported positive cases indicate mild or severe fever, weak respiratory performance, and other gastrointestinal symptoms, including vomiting, diarrhea, abdominal pain, and nausea. Regardless, it showed minor or no symptoms upfront, which explains why 14 days of evaluation or quarantine is highly advisable by the World Health Organization (WHO). Alongside the difficulties of symptoms, ruled out trivial information concerning the transmission methods; consequently, dispersing the Covid-19 outbreak on a global scale, with the first and second cases outside of China reported in Thailand and Japan, respectively. In less than a month, the virus promptly spread to various parts, including America, Europe, and the United Arab Emirates; thus, the WHO officially confirmed human to human transmission of the coronavirus and advised using masks in the community to prevent the spread of the virus. In addition to masks, constant temperature checks and social distancing are also recommended to slow down the escalation of the outbreak. Apart from preventive measures, exchanges of information are also encouraged to prevent and control the spread of the pandemic and initiate vaccines and treatment development. With the preventive measures and restrictive policies for two years, active step is evident as almost 50% of the population has been vaccinated worldwide. The Covid-19, on an overall scale, left the world in chaos with economic and social consequences, affecting trade, tourism, education, with business and school closures for almost two years. In defiance of preventive measures, social distancing, hygienic practices, positive cases, and death rate do not flag. However, the increased complication of the pandemic paves the way for new resolution as several countries, including Singapore and Europe, are now adapting to the new normal, despite the double rising cases, instead of eradicating the coronavirus. Digital platforms are highly encouraged for institutions to reciprocate the duties and foster new learning styles. At the same time, personal responsibility and information exchanges are perpetually ensured to cope with the outbreak of the virus. In this regard, Southeast Asian nations are not spared from the backlash. The region is becoming a "Global hotspot" in the fight against the Covid-19 positive cases reached up to 200 million out of 600 million population in October 2021. Despite achievement on healthcare policies illustrated by countries like Singapore, Thailand, and Cambodia initially, challenges remain with the emergence of Alpha and Delta variants of Covid-19 following by April 2021 (which may have spread faster than the standard variants). On the bright aspects, 50% of the population has been fully vaccinated despite the limited vaccine rollout and political instability. However, adapting to the new normal should be the next focal point for many to return to the pre-pandemic lifestyle.

Even with perplexing circumstances and unforeseeable threats, Cambodia has carried out a satisfactory payoff in controlling the situation compared to fellow ASEAN members. The country repercussions the first and the second community case outbreak in August and November 2019 accordingly with collective testing and quarantine of relevant

individuals. The actualization remains evident during the third wave of the community outbreak or the 20th February event. Notwithstanding the limited resources and healthcare facilities, infected cases decline from a thousand to less than 500 cases in just five months, in addition to 90% of the population is fully vaccinated. Simultaneously, schools and businesses started to roll back with safety regulations and practices after months of the blockade. Political stability is also highly secured to enhance international relations and ripen subtle benefits during this challenging time.

This article intends to achieve the following objectives: (1) Indicating an overview of the Covid-19 situation in Cambodia, particularly the third wave. (2) Looking upon the strategies imposed by the government on education and economic sectors. (3) Understanding the intensification of international relations at the height of educational and economic stumbling blocks and (4) Scrutinizing the outcomes of the policies implemented and evaluating the effectiveness in comparison with other ASEAN members

II. STRATEGIC IMPLEMENTATION

Despite limited resources and inadequate health care facilities, Cambodia performs significantly well in maintaining the low number of imported positive cases with no death rate amid the early stage. The success remains evident following the community outbreak by the end of 2020 due to effective governing policies such as school and business closures, deploying safety measures in public places, and banning religious event celebrations. In addition, effective tackling on the border policies with the neighboring countries also contributes to the outbreak's lose edge, particularly on the migrant workers and international students. However, even with restrictive measures in place, Cambodia remains vulnerable to the outrage diseases which lead to the severe community outbreak until the present known as "18th February Event," with 116,140 cases reported as of October 2021. In the fight against the Covid-19, WHO, toward the Royal Government of Cambodia, everyone will need to play their roles correspondingly. On that note, respective ministries in Cambodia act accordingly, including the "Stop Covid-19 QR Code", imposing lockdown, mass testing, and implementing vaccination rollout programs across the country. On the bright side, the government and citizens slowly familiarized themselves with the outbreak and the restrictive measures.

In contrast, private institutions and business cooperation reciprocal responsively to imposed regulations on their institutions, employ and operate collectively to effectuate the policies outcome. Nevertheless, the Covid-19 remains a challenge for both developed and underdeveloped countries; thus, the Cambodian government makes clear pathways and strategies to overcome the relevance effect while ensuring stability and preparing for the recovery stages. In that regard, the government of Cambodia has taken active steps to cope with the impacts on the education and economic sectors.

A. Education

In an alignment with the restrictive measures deployed by the Cambodian government against Covid-19, school-at-all-level forced to shut down nationwide, minimize spreading of Covid-19 among teachers and students, by which the decision to open or close all the educational institutions varies upon the number of cases and the containment of the spread of the virus by relevance ministries. The school suspension produces a number of consequences on the quality of education as the lack of a monitoring system and a sudden switch toward digital platforms could be challenging for many teachers and students. In addition, the demand for enhancing technological advancement remains vital, especially for vulnerable children or schools in remote areas of the country, as the lack of access to educational resources left many to drop out of school amid the pandemic. On the surface, the Covid-19 affects merely the school operation; deep down, the whole education system in countries is affected by the changes that spillover to the strategic plan, financial budget, and the psychological health of those in the educational community. In the early stage of the outbreak, the funding on the educational sector was cut by 30%, which affected the Ministry's policy reform in promoting life-long learning and enhancing the quality of education across the country. Thus, an immediate response plan is needed to address the challenges and to put educational development back in its place. The goals are to ensure continuous learning at all levels, ensure safety for students and academic staff, and prepare for school reopening in the nearest future. To achieve these objectives, the Ministry of Education Youth and Sport (M.O.E.Y.s) cooperates closely with the E.S.W.G. members and a number of N.G.O.s in Cambodia to facilitate and implement the online learning program and continue to provide information about the spread of Covid-19. Initially, e-learning through television and official Facebook pages for primary and secondary schools were introduced so that students from respective levels could continue accessing educational resources. However, just like other countries, the sudden switch to digital platforms is still undermined by a number of issues, including access to devices and internet stability.

Meanwhile, learning effectiveness remains challenged as teachers and students need to change their behavior and slowly adapt to the new learning approaches. To assist the implementation of the new ways of learning, the M.O.E.Y.s provide capacity training for teachers and educational staff on technical knowledge, which allow teachers to create group chats to

engage with students and eventually conduct several activities like paper-based worksheets to closely monitor student's activities and do some mental health check; thus, students are also encouraged to conduct more self-study to reap the benefits of online learning. In addition to teaching, teachers are also responsible for promoting hygienic practices, Covid-19 preventive measures, and 3Dos and 3Donts in the spike of the pandemic so students can adapt to the new normal and pave ways for school reopening. Another step taken to set out school reopening was the vaccination rollout policies by the government of Cambodia, which prioritize teachers and educational staff and eventually students from 6 years old and above. The vaccination priorities do not include only the first and the second doses but also the third dose. However, the vaccination policies do not imply the ignorance of the Covid-19 breakout as public places and educational institutions, both public and private, need to operate regarding restrictive measures and guidelines imposed by the government.

Despite several alternatives to education in its track, all the policies still aim for safe school reopening at the recovery stages. Initially, regular testing for teachers and academic staff is compulsory to monitor the detected cases at specific places while keeping students safe while they are at school. In addition, reasonable safety measures are highly ensured, including hygienic practices, social distancing, temperature checks, and wearing masks. To support the effectiveness of policy implementation, assistance and support are provided to the school, teachers, and students by the M.H.P.S.S., which includes technicality and physical and mental health support in this challenging period. Last but not least, to ensure the policies can be carried out effectively, the government also introduced the monitoring and evaluation measures by which ministers and relevant officials have to oversee the practices of the school as failure to comply might lead to suspension and closure. The policy implies to local students and includes Cambodian students who pursue their education abroad. Unlike other countries, evacuating students from high-rated infected countries was not encouraged, instead was urged to remain in the designated countries for the time being because we should not leave each other during this challenging time, and quitting can further spread the virus to many places. To ensure the safety of students, the Cambodian embassy in foreign countries was asked to arrange a safe location for Khmer students to study online and assist their necessities during their stay. Despite the urge, students still have the freedom to decide whether or not they wish to return to Cambodia, as indicated that until July 2020, Cambodian students from several countries are returning to Cambodia. Thus, restrictive measures, quarantines, and constant testing are required upon arrival. For almost two years, many countries' borders remained closed, which is why the Moeys strongly encouraged students to continue pursuing their education on the virtual platform while diplomatic steps are still in progress to ensure students can safely return in the near future.

B. Economic

In Cambodia, garment industrial, tourism, agriculture, construction, and other light manufacturing are regarded as the engine of economic growth. Cambodia concentrates mainly on trade openness and capital flow, attracting many foreign investors and eventually expanding the market to other parts globally. In addition, a sector of the economy also comes from small and medium enterprises (S.M.E.s), mainly in the services sector. The industries have given thousands of jobs to millions of people across the countries, which constantly decreases the country's poverty rate. Unfortunately, with the emergence of Covid-19, traveling restrictions and restrictions were more complicated than ever, requiring health certificates, insurance, quarantines, proof of vaccination, and other charges, which eventually led to a significant decline in the tourism sector bankruptcy. The border policy also impacts the FDI flows and investors as some countries temporarily closed their borders due to containment measures that have dramatic consequences on the garment export in Cambodia. The border closure does not only cause a drop in remittance and takes away the jobs and revenues of many people. Only bike manufacturing showed a sign of the increase in export during the Covid-19 pandemic, while others still suffer from the loss as they are hard to substitute with technology. The most affected sectors would be the "unnecessary business," including entertainment industries like cinema and theatre. The government has issued a temporary closure to cope with the spread of Covid-19. As for agricultural sectors, there was a substantial increase in the demand for rice and food storage exports, which allowed the country to expand trade to various countries, including China, the U.S., Europe, and other ASEAN countries, despite the ban on the fishery products.

Cambodia retains the advantages of a stable political environment and seizes the chances to develop the food-producing sectors during this time while exporting from neighboring countries declines. Even though there are minor impacts on farming and shipping, the price of the products falls dramatically following the outbreak, which hinders the farmers' ability to pay back debt. Thus, many businesses are conducting and enhancing advertising online on the bright side. In contrast, other industries that consist of low-skilled labor forces still have to deal with the issues of lockdown, restrictive measures, or job loss. At the initial point, humanitarian aid is provided to those in the lockdown area, particularly workers, by supplying food, necessities, and cash to support their needs during this lockdown.

Meanwhile, the government also allocated more budget to health sectors to sustain more medical equipment for quarantine sites, enhance the ability to conduct testing regularly and where relevant, and enforce the scan Q.R. code to keep

track of the infected cases easier. For the industries affected, the government strongly encouraged the implementation of virtual alternatives for feasible sectors. Furthermore, constant political stability needs to be ensured while introducing free tax holidays and other incentives for investing in Cambodia to attract more investors into the countries. The government also cooperates with the relevant international organizations, including A.D.B., I.M.F., UNDP, WHO, to provide more financial support both on the bilateral and multilateral level to rescue the sectors affected by the economic shock.

Moreover, the government also eases the local travel restriction to support local tourism. The excellent progress for international tourists is that the number of days for quarantine is simplified from 14 days to 7 days and now to no quarantine for vaccinated tourists. In addition, procedures and insurance policies are now less complicated to attract more international tourists upon the recovering stages. Most importantly, the government has introduced the nationwide vaccination program targeting a 10 million population. The priority is based upon the degree of vulnerability of the occupation of the citizens running from medical workers, government officials, armies and police officers, teachers and business cooperation, and regular citizens. Several vaccination points were deployed across the country to realize this national ambition, including public hospitals, pagodas, and even schools as the center to get the vaccination. It is accessible for people who wish to get the vaccination and at the same time is free of charge for everyone. Even though recovering from the Covid-19 outbreak remains slow, step-by-step progress is taken to adapt to the new normal quickly. On this aspect, the government also aims at expanding international partnership and international cooperation to improve the prestige and collaborate for mutual benefits. At the initial stage, Cambodia was a limited resources country with technical disadvantages. Yet, the government managed to earn much support from international organizations in both financial and technical support to fight against the Covid-19. The country was listed among the priorities to receive vaccines from the Covax Program and bilateral partners like China and Japan's donation. Despite having difficulties, Cambodia also showcased generosity in helping other countries by providing vaccination and other medical equipment to widespread neighboring countries like Vietnam and Laos. At the height of conducting Covid-19 diplomacy, Cambodia is also an active participant among other conferences and international meetings, by which the countries have endorsed and ratified the ASEAN declaration on Covid-19.

III. DEVELOPMENT AND OUTCOMES ANALYSIS

In the back of imposing strategies, Education and Economic sectors, the aftermath of the actions should also be determined to evaluate the effectiveness of such initiatives. At the same time, progress and further steps will also be incorporated into this part.

A. Educations

The developments of the approaches on educational development admit the Covid-19 pandemic shall be underlain upon The Ministry of Education in Cambodia: Education Response Plan to Covid-19. The apparent actualization showcases that schools across the country are allowed to reopen after two years of uncertainty and rapid closure. The reopening is conducted with high protection to safeguard and control the spread of the diseases within the school area. The ministries announce regular rapid tests of teachers and students. At the same time, social distancing and maintenance of sanitation and hygiene could be spotted in the schoolzone. To ensure the effectiveness and regular practices of the restrictive measures at school and public places, monitoring and evaluation by the M.O.E.Y.s have been constantly implemented to ensure the rules since the inappropriate practices will eventually lead to the schools' fine. The most substantial key behind this achievement was the vaccination rollout program which gives priorities to teachers and academic staff as the front-liners for educational pathways, while children and teenagers from 6 and above (school-starting age) are allowed to be vaccinated so that risks and spread can be minimized upon returning to school. Another noteworthy aspect is the inclusiveness of the procedures toward the vulnerable groups, particularly in the remote area with several vaccination campaigns, outreach activities, and humanitarian aids corporate with the Ministry and N.G.O.s. Meanwhile, it is undeniable that Covid-19 is a threat to the development of quality education; integrating teachers and students with technologies is acknowledged, allowing Cambodia to move a step closer to digital transformation. The qualities of education will remain as the challenges, yet the factors mentioned above pave the way and support M.O.E.Y.'s expectations on the recovery of education in the post-Covid-19 pandemic.

Externally, many countries decided to reopen the border for low-risk nations and vaccinated students to return, which are great opportunities for Cambodian students who pursue their education. Unfortunately, complete reopening does not apply to all countries as many students remain in the country and study online with their designated country's border temporarily closed. While diplomatic discourse marks a great initiative, constant interaction between university and students shall stand as the journey to normality is still a lingering process.

B. Economic

February 20th was a rough time for Cambodia; thus far, the number of cases has gone down dramatically from almost 1000 cases per day in June to less than 100 cases per day by October 2021. The positive indication allowed the country to completely reopen, as Prime Minister Hun Sen announced in late October that Cambodia is now reopened for vaccinated tourists, paving the way for tourists' industries locally, which is the heart of the economy of Cambodia. The reopening was layout by a few indicators. At the outset, doctors and medical workers are now more experienced in coping with the outbreak than the first and second outbreak, so controlling the re-escalation is highly feasible. The fascinating factor was the adaptability of the people, and their behavior toward the Covid-19, by which panicking and chaos at the initial outbreak, are now replaced with more knowledge and understanding on the pandemic. The accustoming is practical with the M.O.H. announced in early November authorizing Covid-19, known as Molnupiravir, for emergency use for treatment against the Covid-19, allowing workers and many private companies to continue doing their business despite the breakout of the cases. Meanwhile, Video of Self-treatment's was publicized on social media platforms and T.V. outlets to provide more knowledge to the people on the treatment against the virus, which is also a positive initiation on the new normal and adaptability for Cambodians. The reopening process and adjusting to the new ways of living would induct the economic recovery of Cambodia.

The pathway for complete reopening also opens up more investors with tax relief policies to invest in Cambodia and restore the economic loss. In addition, technical and financial supports are given to support further trade and affected industries, including garments, food, and agriculture, as indicated by several extensions of bilateral F.T.A. Alongside economic recovery, political stability is maintained. Compared with other ASEAN members, Cambodia has the highest vaccination rate among the ASEAN countries, with 90% of the population aged 6+ vaccinated and strict implementation of 3rd dose. Cambodia has also provided medical aids and vaccines to neighboring countries fighting against the Covid-19. The government extends their most excellent support, particularly Lao P.D.R. and the Socialist Republic of Vietnam. Cambodia illustrates both capacities in stabilizing the country while promoting unity and prestige in the region.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the achievements accomplished by Cambodia in the fight against Covid-19 is a remarkable phenomenon, despite being a low-resource developing state and critical challenges of Covid-19 variant in the 20th February Event. The miraculous realization is evident, plummeting from 1130 cases per day in June to less than 20 cases per day in December 2021. Apart from the number of instances, Cambodia also has the highest vaccination rate in ASEAN and one of the highest globally by which the rate goes beyond the targeted population (10 million), which stays at 88.96% over 16 million populations, 13.5 million of which have received the second dose. In contrast, 2.5 million receive the third dose as of December 2021. The success story of Cambodia was not a coincidence but consisted of both strategic planning and rapid implementation of policies imposed toward the education and economic sectors. The government has introduced online learning for all students in response to school closure and provides capacity building for teachers to ensure continuous learning. At the same time, many preparations were made for school-reopening progress, including testing, imposing restrictive measures at school and public places, and vaccination programs. Economically, the government also proposes several alternatives for affected sectors, including humanitarian support, trade expansion and FDI attraction, and ease of travel bans and restrictions. Despite recovering at a slow phase, the results illustrate the safe opening of schools after almost a year of closure, national exams under constant monitoring, and compliance with restrictive measures. Cambodia also announced the complete reopening in early November, allowing more tourists and investors to rescue the local industries in the country and trade and export expansion. Even though there were several obstacles alongside, it is undeniable that Cambodia is now winning the fight against Covid-19 and has managed to seize development in the post-recovery stage. The achievement on a local scale does not stop Cambodia's potential as the government is now aiming to expand this potential on a regional scale, particularly on ASEAN in the next phase of 2022 chairmanship.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Nit, Buntongyi, et al. "Understanding the slow COVID-19 trajectory of Cambodia." *Public Health in Practice* 2 (2021): 100073.
- [2] Waithaka, John, et al. "Impacts of COVID-19 on protected and conserved areas: A global overview and regional perspectives." *Parks* 27 (2021): 41-56.

- [3] SETHA, MrNGUON, and PHNOM PENH. "SMEs Contributions to Improving Economic Development in Cambodia: Case study before and after Covid-19." (2020).
- [4] CHOOKAJORN, T., KOCHAKARN, T., WILASANG, C. et al. Southeast Asia is an emerging hotspot for COVID-19. *Nat Med* 27, 1495–1496 (2021).
- [5] BANGA, KARISHMA, and DIRK WILLEM TEVELDE. "Cambodia, COVID-19 and inclusive digital transformation: a seven-point plan." *Supporting Economic Transformation*. London (2020).
- [6] *Coronavirus (COVID-19) Vaccinations - Statistics and Research* Available: (<https://ourworldindata.org/covid-vaccinations>)
- [7] *WHO's COVID-19 response* Available: (<https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/interactive-timeline>)
- [8] *WHO works closely with the Royal Government of Cambodia in the fight against COVID-19* Available: (<https://www.who.int/cambodia/news/detail/12-05-2020-who-works-closely-with-the-royal-government-of-cambodia-in-the-fight-against-covid-19>)
- [9] *MoEYS, Cambodia Education Response Plan to COVID 19 Pandemic* Available: (https://planipolis.iiep.unesco.org/sites/default/files/ressources/cambodia_education_response_plan_to_covid19_panademic_july_2020.pdf)
- [10] *MoEYS, Cambodia Education Response Plan to COVID 19 Pandemic* Available: (https://planipolis.iiep.unesco.org/sites/default/files/ressources/cambodia_education_response_plan_to_covid19_panademic_july_2020.pdf)
- [11] *Cambodias-agriculture-sector-amid-covid-19* Available: (<https://opendevelopmentcambodia.net/km/cambodias-agriculture-sector-amid-covid-19/>)
- [12] *Khmer times news, Ministry of Health releases "Guidelines for the Management and Treatment of COVID-19 in the Kingdom of Cambodia" document* Available: (<https://www.khmertimeskh.com/50911151/ministry-of-health-releases-guidelines-for-the-management-and-treatment-of-covid-19-in-the-kingdom-of-cambodia-document/>)
- [13] *The Phnom Penh Post: PM declares Cambodia fully reopen from Nov, 1st* Available: (<https://www.phnompenhpost.com/national/pm-declares-cambodia-fully-reopen-nov-1>)